

**TYPES OF DEVELOPING PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS'
SKILLS IN CONDUCTING INTERACTIVE LESSONS****Nisanbayeva Akmaral****Professor, National Pedagogical University
of Uzbekistan named after Nizami****Islomova Fotima****Student, National Pedagogical University
of Uzbekistan named after Nizami****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17906393>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 09th December 2025Accepted: 10th December 2025Online: 11th December 2025**KEYWORDS**

Students will become the driving force of the educational process, ensuring quality and effectiveness

ABSTRACT

The main content of this article is enriched with reflections on the use of learner-centered education and its intended purposes, based on theoretical and scientific-practical data related to improving the professional competence of primary school teachers..

Modern schools have been provided with a new generation of textbooks, modernized curricula, and improved standards that have undergone experimental testing. The material and technical base of schools is being strengthened. New school buildings are being constructed, reconstruction and routine or major repairs are carried out; schools are supplied with modern equipment, technical facilities, and digital tools, while programs for the social protection and material or moral encouragement of students and teachers are being implemented.

Regardless of how well the material base of schools develops or how much textbooks, curricula, and standards are improved, ensuring deep and solid knowledge for students and teaching them to think freely and creatively ultimately depends on the professional mastery and competence of teachers, on the extent to which they have mastered modern lessons, advanced technologies, and the skills of organizing interactive learning.

A fundamental question arises: *Can today's pedagogical university graduates organize lessons using new methods that correspond to new conditions?*

Innovative technologies, new pedagogical approaches, and especially interactive learning—recognized as key factors ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education—have become a pressing necessity.

This, in turn, requires humanizing, liberalizing, and democratizing the educational process; building friendly relations with children; and organizing learning in cooperation and co-creativity. In short, the learner must stand at the center of the educational process. The teaching process must be directed toward and focused on the learner.

Learner-centered education functions as a driving force that organizes the learning activities of students, reveals their interests, desires, and needs, and motivates them toward learning. So what does individualization in the teaching process mean?

Learner-Centered Education in the Teaching Process Includes:

- Increasing student activity;

- Teaching students to think independently;
- Organizing creative thinking;
- Ensuring student independence and freedom;
- Conducting instruction based on students' interests (motivation);
- Activating students' potential abilities;
- Guiding students toward additional learning (extracurricular, out-of-school);
- Supporting self-development and self-education

Developing these personal characteristics leads to the formation of students' skills and competencies for independent learning.

It is well known that graduates of pedagogical universities generally master most of the subjects taught in primary education; however, they face difficulties in planning, preparing, and conducting lessons using modern methods. How can they acquire these skills during their student years?

It is no secret that reforming the educational process must begin with reforming the lesson itself. Where should lesson reform begin?

- A responsible attitude toward the lesson;
- Introducing new approaches to teaching;
- Individualizing instruction in the classroom;
- Organizing lessons based on student activity, collaboration, and co-creation;
- Using interactive, innovative, and advanced technologies.

Our observations and the study of advanced foreign experiences show that preparing future teachers to conduct interactive lessons can yield positive results if organized in the following three directions:

Direction

From the first year to graduation, students should be taught—through courses in psychology, pedagogy, methodology, informatics, and pedagogical practice—the theoretical foundations, content, and mechanisms of implementing interactive teaching.

II. Direction

Each group should form small creative teams of 5–6 students who study and master interactive teaching. After learning each method, they must conduct seminar-trainings, round-table discussions, and debates according to a special schedule. A continuous system of peer teaching and mutual learning should be established.

III. Direction

Students should be guided to conduct scientific-pedagogical research based on personal study plans. Throughout the academic year, they should search for and collect scientific-methodical literature, periodical materials, advanced pedagogical experiences, and internet resources, create a database, and utilize it in practice.

Traditional vs. Interactive Teaching: Meaning, Essence, and Differences

Passive Method (Traditional Teaching)

The learner assimilates material from the teacher's speech, explanations, storytelling, and narration. Homework is completed by reading textbooks and manuals. No feedback

system exists between teacher and student, and mastery depends solely on the learner's interest, ability, and desire.

Shortcomings:

- Lack of feedback;
- Learning activities are carried out mainly by the teacher;
- Students remain passive listeners lacking independence;
- Lessons follow a monotonous pattern;
- Everything depends on the teacher.

Authoritarian Pedagogy. Active Method.

Widely used in traditional teaching. The teacher uses all their skills to explain content effectively with visual aids and didactic materials. Students are involved in discussions, creative activities, and problem-solving. Collaboration between teacher and students creates greater engagement and increases learning efficiency.

Interactive Method

An interactive lesson provides an environment conducive to creative thinking. Students exchange ideas actively, engage in mutual information sharing, collaboratively discuss and solve problems, and demonstrate their knowledge to one another. Each participant experiences authorship of the learning content, achieving deep understanding and high performance

Interactive comes from the English word "interact" (**inter - mutual; act - action**), meaning *mutual activity and influence*.

Interactive learning forms skills in teamwork, collaboration, and written expression. It does not reject traditional methods but enhances lesson content through mutual activity and co-creation.

Main Interactive Teaching Methods

- Problem-based learning;
- Project-based learning;
- Game-based learning;
- Creative learning;
- Heuristic learning;
- ICT-based learning.

Interactive learning involves dialogue, collaboration, and mutual influence between teacher and students. Its core goal is to create the most favorable conditions for students' active, free, and creative thinking.

Interactive lessons ensure that no student remains passive. Every participant openly expresses thoughts and conclusions based on what they hear, read, see, and understand. This fosters sincerity, interest in learning, mutual support, and friendly relationships.

Students learn individually, in pairs, and in small groups. Lessons may include research-based tasks, role-playing, planning, algorithmization, modular learning, working with textbooks and documents, using informational sources, and performing creative tasks.

Steps for Organizing Interactive Lessons

- Selecting the topic and content;
- Determining the lesson's overall educational goal;

- Identifying theoretical and practical knowledge to be taught;
- Defining key concepts, skills, and competencies;
- Choosing lesson format, methods, and tools;
- Estimating time allocation for each element;
- Developing exercises and problem sets;
- Preparing tests and questions for assessment;
- Establishing the sequence and concluding mechanisms for the lesson.

Changing Roles of Teachers and Students in Interactive Learning

- The teacher transforms from a knowledge transmitter into a facilitator, consultant, organizer, and guide;
- Teachers must master algorithmizing, modularization, project design, and co-creative thinking;
- They must teach not only *knowledge* but also *how to learn*;
- Students must be given conditions to work independently, in pairs, and in groups;
- Individualization must be ensured so that mastery of content becomes guaranteed.

Conclusion

If future teachers are trained to work interactively:

- Graduates will develop motivation toward innovation and the skills to apply new methods in lessons;
- Through continuous work in classes and creative groups, they will form stable competencies in using interactive methods;
- Upon entering schools, vocational colleges, and academic lyceums, they will be able to effectively implement advanced technologies;

Students will become the driving force of the educational process, ensuring quality and effectiveness.

References:

1. Dilova N.G'. The role of cooperative pedagogy in the development of the learner's personality. *Modern Education*, Issue 1 (2017).
2. Indiaminov N. et al. Learner-centered education in increasing the effectiveness of teaching. *Educational Technologies*, 2014(8).
3. Nisanbayeva, A. (2023). The importance of using innovative methods and approaches in teaching the native language. *Science and Innovation*, 2(B2), 177–178.
4. Nisanbayeva, A., & Chinaliyeva, A. (2022). The importance of motivation in human activity. *Science and Innovation*, 1(Special Issue 2), 781–786.